

Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Education in the Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This research article aimed to assess the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Education activities and its effects to the lives of the learners in the Philippines during the School Year 2019-2020. The findings revealed that the respondent's awareness and knowledge of the practices on what to do before-during-after disasters like fire, flood, typhoon and earthquake were very much knowledgeable. It also publicized that the level of awareness among respondents on the DRR activities such as lecture and video presentation, picture and story show, drawing and coloring, DRR jingle and Evacuation Drills were very much enhanced. It was concluded that through DRR Education in the Philippines, the learners may be able to easily build their knowledge on various natural disasters and through the use and proper application of DRR activities, their interest and desire will increase in order to take appropriate action for disaster preparedness and mitigation, thus, reducing its risks and impacts.

KEYWORDS: Disaster Risk Reduction Education Activities, Pillars, Cebu, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The goal of education is to change individuals behaviors Mindfulness about dangers and risks need to begin in early education before capacities to address them can turn out to be a piece of becoming community and expert obligations as individuals develop.

Education can have a catalytic result to toughen communities and lessen vulnerability. This was acknowledged, by governments throughout the world in the Sendai Framework, which calls for "a culture of prevention and education on disaster risk." The Asia Pacific Region is the most disaster-prone region in the world, facing numerous hazards, from severe flooding to storms to volcanic eruptions to tsunamis and earthquakes (Maplecroft, 2017).

It is recognized that the Philippines is prone to cataclysmic events and catastrophes because of its topographical area. Likewise, man-made catastrophes, wrongdoings and demonstrations of psychological warfare put the lives of the Filipinos in question. These crisis conditions, regardless of whether regular or man-made, are generally referred to as incidents that requires response actions.

Republic Act (RA) 10121 otherwise known as the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010, mandated all government agencies to institutionalize policies, structures, coordination mechanisms and programs with continuing budget appropriation on disaster risk reduction at all levels.

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Moreover, RA 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 vested the department of Education (DepEd) with the authority, accountability, and responsibility to ensure access to basic education which is often disrupted by emergencies and disasters.

With the diversion brought by dangers, there is a need to discover systems bolster materials receptive to the adapting needs of youngsters and instructing methodologies that could adjust to crisis circumstances, thus are mandated to implement or integrate disaster risk reduction education in the curriculum.

Pillar 3 of the Comprehensive School Safety Framework under Quality species the integration of Disaster Risk Reduction DRR/ CCA Climate Change Adaptation in the K to 12 curriculums the constraints to access, along with the psychosocial condition of learners and teachers, affect the quality of education.

DepEd Order 37, s. 2015. "The Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in the Basic Education Framework, stipulates the following objectives a.) Protect learners and education workers from death, injury, and harm in schools; b.) Plan for educational continuity in the face of expected hazards and threats; c.) Safeguard education sector investments; and d.) Strengthen the risks reduction and resilience through education.

The human ideal to instruction is imperative and all inclusive. It enables individuals to achieve their maximum

capacity and enables them to practice different rights. In “The Convention on Rights of the Child and Education’ knowledge about the natural environment is also specified (UNICEF, 2007). It could then be contended that DRR education draws near this category.

Learners are viewed as performers inside DRR. They are more subject to impact are subsequently observed as seek after what's to come. Not exclusively would they be able to be taught to respond in a viable way when a characteristic peril strikes, they can likewise be instructed regarding why these dangers are progressively occurring and the systems that can be taken to decrease vulnerability.

Learners will decide how the future will be: they are the next great politicians, disaster planners or managers, and teaching them about disasters could conceivably notably affect maintainable advancement, flexibility and accomplishment of development goals

DRR Education in the Philippines

The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines issues the enclosed Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in Basic Education Framework under DepEd order 37, s. 2015 to guide DRRM efforts in the basic education sector towards resilience-building in offices and schools, and to ensure that quality education is continuously provided and prioritized even during disasters and/or emergencies.

This Framework shall institutionalize DRRM structures, systems, protocols and practices in schools. Further, this shall provide common understanding and language in the implementation of DRRM in basic education at all levels and is expected to guide schools in assessing, planning and implementing their specific prevention and mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery, and rehabilitation.

There are three pillars in this framework that includes the following:

Pillar 1: Safe Learning Facilities. This pillar refers to the physical and other related structures of the school. It also includes the establishment of temporary learning spaces that can be used during possible displacement brought by disasters and /or emergencies.

Pillar 2: School Disaster Management. This pillar refers to the establishment of organizational support structures such as the DRRM service and DRRM coordinator in the school. This shall also cover the setting up of systems, processes and standards to operationalize the four thematic areas in the context of education.

Pillar 3: Risk Reduction and Resilience Education. This refers to the integration of DRRM in the formal and non-formal school curricula and in extra-curricular or school activities. It should also provide the necessary material support. This covers building the capacity and skills of learners and personnel, particularly teachers through conducts of orientations, workshops and trainings related to Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DO 37 s. 2015).

The integration of disaster risk reduction in education has been one of the advocacies of the DRR community.

Developing a sense of disaster preparedness and equipping the students with risk reduction capacities are ways to reduce their vulnerabilities and build their resilience to disaster (Luna, 2017) Based on the new K to 12 curriculums, disaster risk reduction educations are integrated from kindergarten to Grade 10 in the subjects. These suggested DRR activities includes the following:

Lecture and Video Presentation: Brief lecture on the (a) safe and danger situations; (b) how to protect oneself from common natural hazards by knowing basic actions that are necessary; (c) structural and non-structural mitigation at home and school. Video presentation on how to prepare and mitigate the impact of common hazards including (a) protecting oneself, (b) structural and non-structural mitigation from the impacts of natural hazards at home and school.

Picture and Story Show: Visual presentation by using pictures and storytelling with illustrations showing (a) comparison of safe and unsafe danger situations; (b) how to prepare from a common hazards including simple actions that a learner may be able to perform on their own.

DRR Drawing and Coloring: Drawing and coloring of risks and impacts of disasters. Learners will also create a poster and slogan making showing how a natural hazard may occur and its mechanism.

DRR Jingle: Listening to the DRR Jingle and learning the song to associate the importance of disaster preparedness or composition of DRR Jingle about natural hazards with analysis and explanation of its causes.

Evacuation Drill: Explaining the importance of conducting evacuation drill and participation in the school drills. Proper behavior during evacuation drills should also be demonstrated (e.g. do not panic and do not push other people and evacuating in an orderly manner)

DRR Reading: Reading words, sentences and /or stories related to DRR such as the possible varied risks and impacts of natural hazards including past disasters.

DRR Writing; Creative writing or essay writing with topics about (a) how they can be prepared from disasters at home and at a school; (b) their role in disaster preparedness together with their family and community.

DRR School Watching: Familiarizing the student on the school surroundings of the safe and danger areas including where to evacuate in case a disaster happens.

DRR Memorial Corner Making: Learners complies various memorabilia such as photos, news article and other items affected by previous disasters and they will make a DRR Memorial in their classroom or in school.

DRR Calculating: Computation of damage cost of properties (Problem Solving, Presentation of Data through Graphs)

DRR Card/Board Game: Playing different DRR-based card/board games to stimulate the awareness of learners in a fun experiential learning process.

Emergency Cooking: Teaching learners various means of survival cooking in case of disasters/emergencies. Learners may be asked to perform/ demonstrate actual survival cooking based on locally available resources using tin cans.

Definitely, the aforementioned activities want to reach the overall DRR education goal that learners will be knowledgeable of the various hazards, its mechanisms and impacts with the ability to perform preparedness measures by themselves, with family and their community (Elnar, 2016)

According to the result of the study of Chen & Lee (2012), the integration of disaster prevention education into formal school curricula; teacher training for campus disaster prevention education; development of a coalition of campus and community-based disaster management; and study of the impact of climate change and school vulnerability are the following items to be stressed in disaster prevention education.

It is important to strengthen disaster reduction education, disseminate disaster reduction knowledge and undertake disaster reduction training. The enhancement of public awareness of disaster risks has laid a foundation for furthering disaster reduction work (China Daily, 2013).

Disaster risk education that promotes risk mitigation and disaster preparedness has been shown to be effective in minimizing the impacts of recurring disasters on urban societies. The recent integration of disaster risk reduction (DRR) into school curricula in developing countries has improved public awareness about hazards and potential disaster risks (Baytiyeh, 2018).

DRR activities can -- and do -- help communities identify and reduce the vulnerabilities families faced by natural disasters. The risk of disaster impact can be reduced by helping communities develop early warning systems, establish risk mapping techniques and hold trainings to teach communities how to reduce their vulnerabilities and protect themselves in the event of a disaster (PR Newswire, 2009).

The role of disaster education is to provide knowledge and information to students and promote measures. To achieve it, students may be encouraged to know disaster risk, collect information related to pre-disaster mitigation, and implement it. Community or student's family should be involved in school disaster education and students should take measures with them or do activities with them. Through these activities, students know how to take measures and make good relationship with community. Taking measures by themselves can raise higher risk perception as well as know how to take measures (Shiwaku, et.al, 2007).

Shaw et al. (2004) conducted the similar study which proposed a framework of disaster education in Japan. The study pointed out that community plays important role for student's awareness and action and hence local community must be involved in disaster education in school.

SUMMARY

This research article aimed to assess the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Education activities in the Philippines during the School Year 2019-2020 as basis for an action plan. Specifically, the study endeavored to seek the information related to DRR as to learners' age and gender and participation on DRR activities. Furthermore, it carried the purpose in identifying the level of awareness of the DRR practices as to fire, flood, typhoon and earthquake and determining the extend of DRR activities that enhanced the awareness of DRR as to lecture and video presentation; picture and story show; DRR drawing and coloring; DRR jingle and evacuation drill. The significant mean difference between the perception of the respondents groups on the activities that enhanced the DRR awareness was also taken into account.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study, it is therefore concluded that through DRR Education, the learners may be able to straightforwardly build their knowledge and awareness on various natural disasters. Moreover, through the use and proper application of DRR activities, their interest and desire will increase in order to take appropriate action for disaster preparedness and mitigation, thus, reducing its risks and impacts. So it was concluded that the activities gave them the idea on how to be prepared when disaster strikes not just in school but also to their vicinity.

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